

Technology-Assisted Teaching and Students' Performance in Literature

Ideza B. Sabado

Dolores Integrated School, Quirino Isabela
Masters Thesis: Isabela State University Cabagan Campus
Author's gmail: nujnujramos1818@gmail.com

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to determine the relationship between the language macro skills and students' performance in studying literature when technology is used and when it is not. The teaching and assessment levels of the five macro skills have been shown by mean, Pearson correlation, and T-test and whether there was significant difference between the pretest and posttest mean scores of the students in technology-assisted teaching and in traditional technology teaching group and significant relationship among the macro skills using the appropriate statistical techniques. A set of 30-item pretest and posttest questions was constructed in speaking, listening, reading, writing, and viewing of which the language competencies were based on the English 10 curriculum guide issued by the Department of Education. In the technology-assisted group, aside from the non-technical media, the students have experienced also technical media support like audio-visual aids using LCD projector, speaker, and TV to use as springboard a piece of literature appealingly, while the traditional technology teaching group execute the traditional mode of studying Literature using textbooks, worksheets, charts, and posters. The anticipated outcome of this study is the identification of which language macro skill should receive the less or the greater use of technology in teaching and studying literature, and the crucial role of technology today in a millennial-born classroom. The results of this study can be used to design workbook and textbook for each of the language macro skill in studying pieces of Literature.

Keywords: Technology-Assisted Teaching, Students' Performance and Literature, etc.

INTRODUCTION

Teaching literature using English as medium of communication inside the classroom requires learners to focus more on the use of target language and at the same time develops a conscious approach in understanding language rules and content. In teaching this subject area, it is typical to involve learners in completing the tasks provided in the textbook but learning will become more engaging when studying literature encompasses the senses of a learner where each of the macro skills will be prolifically attained.

Literature and technology have always been integrated in the teaching-learning process. With the advent of technology, the modern ways of learning that is taking place inside the four corners of the classroom have transformed the learners to be responsible of their own learning thereby creating a learner-centered environment. The onset of technology in teaching delivers an opportunity for the learners to have an interesting and meaningful learning experience in a literature classroom.

Research findings show that using technological tools has specific benefits and these include assisting of students in accessing digital information efficiently and effectively, giving support to student-centered and self-directed learning to develop critical thinking skills, producing a creative learning environment, promoting collaborative learning and improving teaching and learning quality.

Conclusively, it is believed that the use of technology creates a positive impact on the students' attitude which may eventually influence their academic performance. The researcher realized that the conduct of this study will reflect the meaningful execution of the cognitive, psychomotor, and affective domains of the teaching-learning process in literature using technology. It is thus imperative that the classroom setting in literature should be restructured in a global perspective to keep attuned to the competencies of 21st century learning.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The researcher made use of the experimental research design. The study assessed the influence of using technology to the student's performances and its relationship between speaking, listening, reading, writing, and viewing in literature.

This study used the Randomized Pretest- Posttest Control Group Design. The pretest was administered to both of the control group and experimental group. The six lessons in a quarter of teacher-made learning plans were employed as basis of determining the behavioral performance of the students. At the end of the execution of the six lessons in a quarter, the post-test was administered.

Sample and Sampling Procedure

The research sample was from the Grade 10-Alpha students of Dolores Integrated School, Quirino, Isabela of the school year 2017-2018. The researcher ranked the sample population based on their general average of forty members into two of which each group had twenty members. In a list, the researcher numbered the names in alphabetical arrangement. The students with even numbers were categorized

under the technology-assisted teaching group while the rest of the students were placed under the traditional technology teaching group.

Research Instruments

The researcher considered the use of learner's material, teacher-made learning plans and teacher-made test to facilitate the conduct of this study.

Learner's Material

The English 9 Learner's Material from the Department of Education (DepED) was obtained as the source of the learning content of literature. It was utilized in designing the six learning plans and in making the 150 teacher-made item test.

Teacher-made Learning Plans

The researcher made use of teacher-designed learning plans. The learning plans were based on English 10 learning material issued by the Department of Education. The researcher constructed and prepared six literature lessons good for the fourth quarter. The literary texts found in the learning plan covers the discussion of literary texts such as *The Little Prince*, *A Martian Sends a Postcard Home*, Chapter VII: *Cossette Side By Side*, Excerpt from *Kaffir Boy*, *The United Fruit Co.*, and *What Does It Mean To Be A Global Citizen?*.

The learning plans also contained varied activities using technical and non-technical media which enhance the students' language ability in speaking, listening, reading, writing, and viewing.

Teacher-made Test

For the purpose of identifying the performance of the students, a 150-item teacher-made test of 30 items in speaking, listening, reading, writing, and viewing was constructed. The said test was taken from the six lessons to be administered. The test was also categorized into the five-macro skill which primarily aimed to distinguish the effect of technology in teaching literature. The reliability of the test has been validated through item analysis.

Data Gathering Procedure

In pursuing this study, the researcher obtained a Grade 10 Learner's Material from the Department of Education as the basis of formulating the objectives and activities intended for making the learning plan.

To determine the students' performance in literature, the 150-item teacher-made test was administered to the technology-assisted group and traditional technology assisted group before (pretest) and after (posttest) undertaking the six lessons. The six lessons in a quarter from the English 10 Learning Material were executed in thirty days which was equal to a quarter.

Each lesson in the technology-assisted teaching class catered activities both in verbal and practical responses such as role-playing, speech delivery, essay writing, and oral reporting, and with the use of technology in the language macro-skills; speaking, listening, reading, writing, and viewing, while the traditional technology teaching class enabled learners in traditional verbal and practical responses such as role playing, speech delivery, and persuasive essay writing.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The data were tallied, tabulated, and computed to enable the researcher in analysing and interpreting the gathered data. The following statistical tools were used:

1. **T-test** is used to describe whether or not the difference between two groups' averages most likely reflects a "real" difference in the population from which the groups are sampled.
2. **Mean** is the average of the numbers: a calculated "central" value of a set of numbers.
3. **Pearson Correlation** is a measure of the strength of a linear association between two variables.

Correlation Value	Description
0.90 – 1.00	High to Very High Relationship
0.60 – 0.89	Substantial Relationship
0.40 – 0.59	Moderate Relationship
0.20 – 0.39	Low Relationship
0.00 – 0.19	Negligible

4. **Descriptive Evaluation** is used to specify the level of learning of the students based on their pretest and posttest scores.

Scores Interval	Description
25 – 30	Very High
19 – 24	High
13 – 18	Fair
7 – 12	Low
0 – 6	Very Low

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter examines the results and discussions of the students' performance in literature using the technology-assisted teaching and traditional technology teaching of the language macro skills.

Pretest Scores

The pretest scores of the students from the thirty-item test in literature in each of the language macro skill are presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Summary of Pretest Mean Scores in the Technology-assisted Teaching and Traditional Technology Teaching Groups in Literature in terms of Language Macro skills

Macro skills	Technology-Assisted Group		Traditional Group	
	Mean	Description	Mean	Description
Speaking	9.10	Low	8.95	Low
Listening	9.75	Low	9.20	Low
Reading	9.00	Low	8.30	Low
Writing	8.40	Low	8.85	Low
Viewing	10.25	Low	9.55	Low

Note: Very High (25-30), High (19-24), Fair (13-18), Low (7-12), Very Low (0-6)

Table 1 shows that the student-respondents in technology-assisted teaching and traditional technology teaching are of equal level in their prior knowledge about the content of the test. And since both groups have not received any treatment or lesson discussions yet, they obtained the same "low" mean scores which fall between 7–12 intervals. This is based on their raw score from a 30-item test in each of the language macro skills. Also, it indicates that the learners are interestingly good enough to further experience learning in literature.

Posttest Scores

The posttest scores of the students from the thirty-item test in literature in each of the language macro skills are presented in Table 2.

Table 2

Summary of Posttest Mean Scores in the Technology-assisted Teaching and Traditional Technology Teaching Groups in Literature in terms of Language Macro skills

Macroskills	Technology-Assisted Group		Traditional Technology Group	
	Mean	Description	Mean	Description
Speaking	19.15	High	17.75	High
Listening	19.45	High	17.30	High
Reading	20.25	High	17.65	High
Writing	19.70	High	18.05	High
Viewing	21.65	High	17.70	High

Note: Very High (25-30), High (19-24), Fair (13-18), Low (7-12), Very Low (0-6)

Table 2 shows the posttest mean scores between the technology-assisted teaching and traditional technology teaching groups. Both post tests mean scores of the groups lie between 19 – 24 score interval. This means they got “high” scores in the 30-item test in each of the language macro skills. However, students in the technology-assisted group obtained higher posttest mean scores against the latter.

Comparison of Pretest Mean Scores

The students’ pretest mean scores in the thirty-item test in each of the language macro skills were compared to determine whether or not the technology-assisted teaching and traditional technology teaching groups are equal or significantly different.

Table 3

Summary of t-values for the Test of Significance of Mean Difference in the Technology-assisted Teaching and Traditional Technology Teaching in Literature in terms of Language Macro skills

Macroskills	Pretest Mean Scores		Mean Difference	T-value	Critical Value
	TATG	TTTG			
Speaking	9.10	8.95	0.15	0.16	0.8727
Listening	9.75	9.20	0.55	0.62	0.5389
Reading	9.00	8.30	0.70	0.33	0.7446
Writing	8.40	8.85	-0.45	-0.60	0.5517
Viewing	10.25	9.55	0.70	0.85	0.4015

Note: TATG (Technology-assisted Teaching Group), TTTG (Traditional Technology Teaching Group), Critical

Value: 2.0244

The table above shows the computed values of t which are consistently not significant since the probability values (p -values) are greater than the critical value at .05 level of significance. This is confirmed further by the fact that the computed t -values are lower than the critical value of t which is 2.0244. This means that the technology-assisted teaching and traditional technology teaching groups are not significantly different in their knowledge of the expected learning outcomes in the five language macro skills.

Comparison of Posttest Mean Scores

The posttest mean scores of the students from the thirty-item test in literature in each of the language macro skills of the technology-assisted and traditional technology teaching groups were compared with the use of t -test as shown in Table 4.

Table 4

Summary of t -values for the Test of Significance of Mean Difference in the Technology-assisted Teaching and Traditional Technology Teaching in Literature in terms of Language Macro skills

Macroskills	Posttest Mean Scores		Mean Difference	T-Value	P- Value
	TATG	TTTG			
Speaking	19.15	17.75	1.40	1.72	0.0939
Listening	19.45	17.30	2.15	2.11*	0.0416
Reading	20.25	18.05	2.20	2.42*	0.0205
Writing	19.70	17.65	2.05	1.99	0.0536
Viewing	21.65	17.70	3.95	5.14**	0.0000

Note: TATG (Technology-assisted Teaching Group), TTTG (Traditional Technology Teaching Group), Critical Value: 2.0244

The t -values in the table above imply that there is a significant difference in the mean scores of the students in terms of their listening, reading, and viewing skills. This is indicated by the computed t -values 2.11, 2.42, and 5.14 respectively, which are higher than the critical value, 2.0244. This is likewise confirmed by the probability values 0.0416, 0.0205, and 0.0000 associated with the said computed t -values which are less than .05.

However, speaking and writing are not significantly different as shown by the computed values of 1.72 and 1.99 which are lower than the critical value, 2.0244. This further supports that student really finds reading as an important and useful tool in the achievement of learning outcomes (Bautista, et al., 2011). Also when technology is used and when students know English as a subject and as a language, the opportunities of listening to good English can aid in the process (Nadeem Khan, et al 2010).

However, speaking and writing are not significantly different as shown by the computed values of 1.72 and 1.99 which are lower than the critical value, 2.0244.

Comparison of Pretest-Posttest Mean Scores in Technology-assisted Teaching

The pretest-posttest mean scores of the students from the thirty-item test in literature in each of the language macro skill of technology-assisted teaching group were compared with the use of t-test as shown in Table 5.

Table 5

Summary of t-values for the Test of Significance of Mean Difference in the Technology –assisted Teaching Method in Literature in terms of Language Macro skills

Macroskills	Technology-assisted Teaching Group		Mean Difference	T-Value	P-Value
	Pretest Mean Scores	Posttest Mean Scores			
Speaking	9.10	19.15	10.05	-17.67***	0.00000000000003
Listening	9.75	19.45	9.70	-19.91***	0.00000000000003
Reading	9.00	20.25	11.25	-20.75***	0.00000000000002
Writing	8.40	19.70	11.30	-17.40***	0.00000000000004
Viewing	10.25	21.65	11.40	-18.34***	0.00000000000002

*Note: The *** indicates that the result is highly significant, while * is significant. Critical Value: 2.093024.*

Table 5 shows that the mean difference pretest and posttest mean scores of students are highly significant. Conclusively, students excel farther in viewing skill when technology is integrated in learning. With mean difference of 11.4, this proves that students can learn very much from looking at film or shorter video clips because they can improve their receptive skills (Lightbown, 2010). Also, listening skill with t-value of -17.67 means “highly significant” and with mean difference of 9.7 against traditional technology teaching because it entails that they are eager to listen when supported with audio clips.

On the other hand, writing skill has a mean difference of 11.3 while reading has a mean difference of 11.25 against traditional technology teaching. The result above is supported with the study of Joshua Bolkan (2017), an online survey administered to

250 teachers in the United States showed that 56% have seen student improvement in reading and writing as well when some aid of technology is applied.

Comparison of Pretest-Posttest Mean Scores of Traditional Technology Teaching

The pretest-posttest mean scores of the students from the thirty-item test in Literature in each of the language macro skills of traditional technology teaching group are presented in Table 6.

Table 6

Summary of t-values for the Test of Significance of Mean Difference in the Traditional Technology Teaching in Literature in terms of Language Macro skills

Macroskills	Traditional Technology Teaching Group		Mean Difference	T-Value	P-Value
	Pretest Mean Scores	Posttest Mean Scores			
Speaking	8.95	17.75	8.8	-15.98	0.000000000002
Listening	9.20	17.30	8.1	-12.49	0.0000000001
Reading	8.65	18.05	9.4	-21.10	0.00000000000001
Writing	8.85	17.65	8.8	-19.78	0.00000000000004
Viewing	9.55	17.70	8.15	-10.99	0.000000000001

Note: Critical Value: 2.093024

Table 6 clearly shows that the student-respondents' pretest and posttest mean scores with the t-value, p-value, and critical value are significant. Reading has highest mean difference 9.4 compare to other skills while listening has the least pretest-posttest mean difference 8.1. As shown with their computed t-value in reading -21.10 and listening -12.49. On the other hand, speaking and reading obtained the same mean difference 8.8 with their computed t -value -15.98 and -19.78. Though it may be traditional tools but still traditional instructions contributed to the learners' acquisition of knowledge and to the development of their skill.

Relationship between the Language Macro skills and Students' Performance in Technology-assisted Teaching

The relationship between the language macro skills and students' performance from the thirty-item test in literature in each of the language macro skills of technology-assisted teaching group were compared with the use of Pearson Correlation as shown in Table 7.

Table 7

Summary of Correlation Values between Language Macro skills inTechnology-assisted Teaching

Macroskills	Speaking	Listening	Reading	Writing	Viewing
Speaking	1				
Listening	0.54*	1			
Reading	0.45*	0.57*	1		
Writing	0.41*	0.78*	0.46*	1	
Viewing	0.72**	0.67**	0.59*	0.52*	1

Note: The * indicates that the value is significant and ** highly significant.

Based on the r values of the skills viewing and speaking with 0.72, listening and writing with 0.78, and listening and viewing with 0.67, it directly described that these skills are of substantial relationship. Moreover, skills that fall under moderate relationships with their r values are speaking and listening with 0.54, speaking and reading with 0.45, speaking and writing with 0.41, listening and reading with 0.57, reading and writing with 0.46, and reading and viewing with 0.59. Table 7 shows that some of the language macro skills are significantly related to each other while viewing has a significant relationship with speaking and listening, and listening with writing. Viewing skill with the highest r value against all the language macro skills indicates the influence of technology in the receptive skills of learners. It strongly supports the statement of Estroga (2012) that viewing is a process that supports oracy and literacy, and is part of an integrated language arts program.” However, with the r value of 0.41 between speaking and writing skills contradicted the study of Rausch (2015) on the relationship between English Speaking and Writing Proficiency and Its Implications for Instruction. Rausch (2015) claims that speaking and writing has the potential relationship dependent to the tasks provided by the teacher. Thus, whether in technology-assisted teaching group or in traditional mode of teaching, speaking skill and writing skill may not really have a significant relationship to each other.

Relationship between the Language Macro skills and Students’ Performance in Traditional Technology Teaching

The relationship between the language macro skills and students’ performance from the thirty-item test in literature in each of the language macro skills of traditional technology teaching group are presented in Table 8.

Table 8

Summary of Correlation Values between Language Macroskills in Traditional Teaching

Macroskills	Speakin g	Listening	Reading	Writing	Viewing
Speaking	1				
Listening	0.20	1			
Reading	0.61**	0.32	1		
Writing	0.20	0.66*	0.49*	1	
Viewing	-0.06	0.68*	0.65**	0.44*	1

*Note: The * indicates that the value is significant and ** means very significant.*

Based on the performance of the students in traditional technology teaching group, viewing and speaking skills are negligible to each other with the r value -0.06. Though viewing means also reading, the learners may have difficulty in decoding details. As a result, the learners may have the hard times expressing about what is seen. Also, speaking skill has r value of 0.20 against listening and writing skills. The “low relationship” of these skills may have a factor from the absence of technical media to assist, enhance, and excite the learners in studying Literature.

On the other hand, the relationship between the skills in speaking and reading, listening and writing, listening and viewing, and reading and viewing are substantial with their r values 0.61, 0.66, 0.68, and 0.65. Aydogan and Akbarov (2014) stated that the four basic skills (speaking, listening, reading, and writing), are related to each other by two parameters: the mode of communication (oral or written) and the direction of communication (receiving or producing the message).

Conclusions

This study highlights the vital role of technology in assessing the students’ performance particularly in speaking, listening, reading, writing, and viewing in teaching literature. The following are the conclusions based on the findings of the study:

1. Media has huge information to offer to learners. Generally, technology-assisted teaching in literature helps in increasing the academic performance of the learners since technology is used as an intervention and motivation to learners.
2. Listening, reading, and viewing skills has relationship to each other and superior against speaking and writing skills. These three skills are receptive or input skills. Therefore, they involve similar thinking processes for decoding information.

3. Performance of students in speaking and writing skills are decreasing as such these skills are not significantly relevant to each other. There are really those who excel in writing but not in speaking and vice versa.

4. The use of technology notably gave factors to align congruently the competencies in each of the language macroskills of learners in literature.

5. Students' performance is highly dependent on the type of instructions used in the teaching-learning process.

6. Listening skill of literature learners are low which strongly shows the imperative part of verbal and practical instructions such as oral reporting, role playing, and speech delivery, to boost and to build up this skill. Besides, the preference that greater degree of traditional instructions of teaching literature and balanced use of technology is a combination to achieve listening skill assessment of the learners to its maximum desired result.

Recommendations

Based on the results in the conduct of this study, the researcher suggests the following statements:

1. Teachers should equally provide the students with repertoire of activities that are not included in the module such as contextualized, localized or indigenized activities or tests.

2. In preparing instructional materials using technology in teaching literature, teachers should always be consistent in inculcating the domains of learning.

3. Listening, speaking, and writing skills of learners should be enhanced with more exposure to technical media in the teaching-learning process in literature.

4. Teachers may attend workshops and seminars to keep updated on the trends in teaching literature.

5. Teachers can develop modules to address the learning deficiency of the students with regard to their ability in acquiring these language skills.

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